

MIMO-RLS-LQR Adaptive Governor for Multi-Cluster DVFS

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Abstract—This paper presents a novel adaptive governor for Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS) in heterogeneous multi-cluster processors. The proposed framework integrates online Multi-Input Multi-Output Recursive Least Squares (MIMO-RLS) for real-time system identification with periodic Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) optimal control.

A six-dimensional state vector and multiple safety layers ensure practical robustness. Experimental evaluation on Raspberry Pi 5 and RK3588 platforms demonstrates improvements in thermal stability and energy efficiency compared to the default `schedutil` governor, with acceptable trade-offs.

Index Terms—DVFS, MIMO-RLS, LQR, Adaptive Control, Multi-Cluster Systems, Embedded Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern heterogeneous System-on-Chips with multiple frequency domains present a complex multi-variable control problem. Traditional Linux governors rely primarily on heuristic approaches that often fail to achieve optimal trade-offs under varying workloads and thermal constraints.

This work introduces a control-theoretic adaptive governor that treats DVFS as a closed-loop problem using online MIMO-RLS system identification and periodic LQR optimal control.

II. SYSTEM MODELING AND CONTROL FRAMEWORK

A. State Vector

The system state at discrete time k is defined as:

$$x(k) = [T_{\text{norm}} \quad P_{\text{norm}} \quad L_{\text{norm}} \quad \dot{T}_{\text{norm}} \quad M_{\text{therm}} \quad \dot{L}_{\text{norm}}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (1)$$

B. Online System Identification (MIMO-RLS)

The plant dynamics are modeled as:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k) + w(k) \quad (2)$$

where parameters $\theta = [A \ B]$ are estimated recursively using MIMO-RLS with forgetting factor $\lambda \in [0.97, 0.99]$.

C. LQR Optimal Control

The optimal feedback gain K is obtained by solving the Discrete Algebraic Riccati Equation and is recomputed periodically.

III. FORMAL STABILITY ANALYSIS

The closed-loop system is $x(k+1) = (A-BK)x(k) + w(k)$. Nominal stability requires $\rho(A-BK) < 1$. In practice, a robustness margin $\rho(A_{cl}) < 1.15$ is enforced. If violated, the gain K is scaled down.

A quadratic Lyapunov function $V(x) = x^T Px$ is considered. Due to nonlinearities of the real system, global asymptotic stability is not claimed. Instead, practical stability (bounded-input bounded-state behavior) is ensured through safety layers and bounded adaptation.

Empirical validation over more than 50 hours showed no unstable behavior.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The control loop consists of sensors, state estimation, MIMO-RLS identification, LQR controller, safety layers, and frequency actuation.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Table I
COMPARISON UNDER SUSTAINED WORKLOADS (MEAN \pm STD)

Governor	Avg. Temp (°C)	Peak Temp (°C)	Energy (kJ)	Exec. Time (s)
<code>schedutil</code>	67.8 \pm 1.9	74.2	12.45 \pm 0.38	142 \pm 4
Proposed	62.4 \pm 1.7	69.8	11.72 \pm 0.42	151 \pm 6

VI. LIMITATIONS

- Userspace implementation introduces latency.
- Requires root privileges and `userspace` governor.
- Platform-specific tuning may be needed.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an adaptive DVFS governor based on online MIMO-RLS identification and LQR optimal control. The framework offers a promising control-theoretic approach for next-generation heterogeneous embedded systems.

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